

Financialization and the Decline of Trade Union Membership in the EU

Gouzoulis Giorgos¹, Galanis Giorgos¹, Panagiotis Iliopoulos²

1. Queen Mary, University of London, UK
2. KU Leuven, Belgium

Summary

1. We investigate the steady fall in trade union membership rates since at least the early 1980s, examining the corporate financialization-induced shift within the EU in the wake of deeper economic integration since 1999.
2. We argue that shareholder value orientation and corporate indebtedness in non-financial firms have been negatively associated with union density in the EU.
3. We underscore that corporate financialization pushes non-financial firms to shift to non-participatory, market-based HR systems that directly undermine the role of trade unions.
4. Policymakers aiming to promote a more egalitarian growth agenda with workers' organizations as key stakeholders should actively advocate for the regulation of shareholder primacy and the imposition of strict rules on downsizing in response to economic conditions.

1. Introduction

The steady fall in union membership rates since at least the early 1980s has been a key area of research for trade unions, policymakers and academics, for the past 25 years. A fast-growing literature within industrial relations, human resource management, and the sociology of work argues that financialization – in the sense of non-financial actors' increasing dependence on financial markets, institutions and instruments – has contributed to the decline of workers' bargaining power and deterioration of their working conditions (for

example, see Gouzoulis et al., 2023; Hanlon and Harney, 2021).

According to this view, non-financial corporations have become increasingly short-termist, prioritizing the maximization of shareholder value over real, long-term investments (Froud et al., 2000; Lazonick and O'Sullivan, 2000). Common practice among non-financial corporations is to maximize dividend payments to shareholders through share buy-backs financed by corporate loans. Recently, the US Congress Research Service has raised significant concerns regarding the scale of cash- and debt-financed share buybacks by US corporations, on the grounds of systematically excessive corporate debt

threatening the sustainability of the financial system (Congressional Research Service, 2019). Earlier this year, the tech giant Apple announced one of the biggest share buybacks program in the history of US companies, reaching \$110 bn (Reinicke, 2024), whereas corporate giants such as “Exxon Mobil, Microsoft, IBM, Visa, Citigroup, Cisco, Pfizer, Oracle, and Bank of America have conducted billion-dollar-plus stock repurchases” (Congressional Research Service, 2019, p. 1). The consequent deterioration of firms’ financial standing as a result of increased interest and dividend payments has been linked to reduced investment, downsizing and the adoption of more ‘flexible’ workforce arrangements as ways of improving the appearance of balance sheets through lower labor costs (for example, Appelbaum and Batt, 2014; Appelbaum et al., 2013; Gospel and Pendleton, 2003; Gouzoulis et al., 2023).

Another implication of financialization with respect to corporate governance is the rise of market-based Human Resources (HR) practices (Thompson, 2003, 2013). Market-based HR systems are generally oriented towards managing human resources without the participation or cooperation of the workers themselves. This approach often leads to employment situations that treat employees simply as ‘resources’, rather than critical stakeholders and constitutive parts of the firm, undermining the role of trade unions and eroding formal negotiations. Another implication of market-based HR systems is the proliferation of unstable employment conditions, with precarious forms of employment and short-term contracts.

This policy brief builds on the results of recently published research, and empirically highlights how corporate financialization, in terms of shareholder value orientation and

increasing corporate debt, has contributed to the decline of trade union density in the EU, since the beginning of the latest phase of EU integration.

2. Financialization, Corporate Governance and Trade Union Membership

Since the beginning of the last phase of European integration, most EU economies have been converging towards an increasingly shareholder value-oriented model of capitalism (Almond et al., 2003). Historically, the EU’s strategy has been to integrate, expand and liberalize the financial and labor markets of its Member States, and to maintain exchange rate stability as a means of improving its international price competitiveness and export performance.

The process of deregulation and harmonization in financial markets and the increased protection of shareholders’ rights across EU Member States has impacted employment relations. Despite lingering national differences, shareholders’ growing influence in Europe has driven business to converge toward the short-termist corporate governance model typical of Anglophone practices (Cernat, 2009; Drobotz and Momtaz, 2020). Predictably, a significant outcome of intensified corporate short-termism is lobbying for the liberalization (deregulation) of employment relations and undermining the role of trade unions in workplaces and broader social agreements across Europe (Almond et al., 2003; Culpepper and Regan, 2014). The weakening of unions’ institutional power means that workers have fewer incentives to join or remain members of unions.

As illustrated in Figure 1, union density has declined sharply across EU countries during the period of rising shareholder pressure. The exception is France, where the unionization rate has remained relatively stable since 2006. It is essential to note, however, that French union density has consistently been lower than in any other EU country since the beginning of the latest phase of EU integration.

Government ideology and labor market institutions are historically important drivers of union density. The ideological leaning of a government towards the left A government's ideological orientation is strongly associated with changes in union membership because labor market regulation and changes in wage-setting institutions implemented by governments affect whether the unions are to play a central role or be marginalized (Gumbrell-McCormick and Hyman, 2013; Masters and Delaney, 2005; Rigby and García Calavia, 2018).

Relevant literature also shows that another crucial factor in the steep decline in unionization rates has been de-industrialization. Because of this structural shift a large portion of the workforce has shifted from highly unionized manufacturing/industrial sectors to low union density occupations in services and even (sometimes bogus) self-employment resulting in the significant decline in trade union membership rates (Blaschke, 2000; Jensen, 2020; Polachek, 2004; Schnabel, 2013).

Union participation is also significantly influenced by external constraints related to the globalization of trade and production networks (Bluestone and Harrison, 1982; Harrison and Bluestone, 1988). The deregulation ('liberalization') of capital flows

that has been escalating since the early 1980s allows employers to easily relocate production to regions with less or unregulated labour markets, where labour costs are comparatively lower in the absence of (strong) unions (Sassoon, 1996; Wallace and Brady, 2001). Segmentation of production can also undermine unionisation as coordination challenges between local unions and foreign employers diminish unions' effectiveness by blurring responsibility in cases of labour rights violations (Western, 1997). Workers in sectors that are central to a particular value chain have more disruptive power, however, and their unions are therefore often more effective, obtaining better working conditions (Iliopoulos et al., 2023).

3. Empirical Analysis and Key Findings

To evaluate the association between the rise of corporate financialization and the decline of unionization rates in the EU during the latest phase of European integration, we follow a panel data econometric approach, utilizing available data for 15 EU countries since 1999, on a set of financial, economic and institutional variables from OECD, ILOSTAT, BIS and the World Bank. The main mechanism behind this trend is that financialization deteriorates firms' financial standing. This financial strain forces firms to adopt more disciplined HR frameworks, resulting in a more flexible workforce, including layoffs of unionized employees to reduce labor costs and avoid paying union wage premiums. Consequently, workers are negatively incentivized to refrain from joining unions to mitigate the risk of redundancy.

Our models statistically associate trade union density with six measures of corporate financialization, namely, corporate

distributed income (OECD), number of listed companies (World Bank), stock market turnover ratio (World Bank), stock market capitalization (World Bank), corporate debt-to-income (BIS) and corporate debt-to-surplus ratio (OECD). Our regression models, following the respective literature, also include controls for capturing the effects of de-industrialization (industrial employment share; World Bank), government ideology (left-right index of governments; Armingeon et al, 2023), labor market regulation (centralization of wage bargaining; Visser, 2019), trade openness (trade-GDP ratio, inflation; OECD).

Our findings provide evidence that the intensification of corporate financialization in the EU over the past 21 years has contributed to the decline of union membership as a result of the pressures imposed by rising corporate debt ratios and a heightened shareholder value orientation on corporate governance in non-financial corporations. In particular, dividend payments have a negative and statistically significant effect on union density, which strongly indicates that shareholder value maximization is indeed linked to lower unionization rates. Similarly, the number of corporations listed on stock markets is found to undermine unionization in the EU, indicating the effects of the spread of shareholder value orientation across the economy (equation (2)).

Furthermore, the stock market trading volume of shares and stock market capitalization have similar effects in terms of size and statistical significance, which provides additional evidence that the volatility and uncertainty arising from non-financial corporations' increasing dependence on stock markets is undermining trade union membership (equations (3) and (4)). Finally, equations (5) and (6) show that increases in

corporate debt ratios are also associated with reductions in union density.

As already mentioned, increased financial payments incentivize managers to undermine unions in order to pass these costs on to workers. Taken together, our results provide robust support in favor of our main argument that indeed union membership has been undermined because of the financialization of corporate governance in the EU since 1999.

4. Conclusions and Policy Implications

In this policy brief, we explored the impact of financialization on unionization rates during the latest phase of EU integration. We argued that a shareholder value orientation and non-financial corporate indebtedness, two key characteristics of the EU integration process, shape firms' governance structures by increasing the importance of maximizing the returns to shareholders and improving their corporate balance sheets, often undermining unions. We show that rising corporate debt ratios, the increasing number of listed corporations, the growth of dividend payments, stock market capitalization, and share trading are strongly associated with decreases in unionization rates.

These findings have significant implications that are relevant for the trade union movement, civil society and policymakers, at different scales (sectoral, national, regional, international). Political parties and transnational policymakers (ETUC, European Union) aiming to promote a more egalitarian growth agenda with workers' organizations as key stakeholders should actively advocate for the regulation of shareholder primacy and the imposition of strict rules on downsizing in response to economic conditions.

Understanding that labor market regulation is not sufficient is fundamental as the interconnection between financial markets, corporate governance strategies and labor management is stronger than ever.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Figures & Tables

Table I. Determinants of union density in the EU, 1999–2019 (FGLS; Time FE).

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>Corporate Distributed Income</i>	-0.116***					
<i>Log(Number of Listed Companies)</i>		-2.942***				
<i>Stock Market Turnover Ratio</i>			-0.009**			
<i>Stock Market Capitalisation</i>				-0.056***		
<i>Non-Financial Corporate Debt</i>					-0.016***	
<i>Non-Financial Corp. Debt-to-Surplus Ratio</i>						-0.643***
<i>Industrial Employment Share</i>	-0.531***	-0.257***	0.231***	-0.158***	-0.712***	-0.751***
<i>Left-Right Index</i>	0.022**	0.031***	0.051***	0.032***	0.018***	0.025***
<i>Bargaining Coordination</i>	8.094***	5.252***	6.143***	5.686***	7.602***	7.203***
<i>Trade Openness</i>	0.009***	0.038***	0.092***	0.087***	0.020***	0.029***
<i>Inflation</i>	-2.136***	-0.704***	-1.730***	-0.670***	-2.510***	-2.091***
<i>Adjusted R²</i>	0.328	0.500	0.446	0.466	0.323	0.329
<i>Observations</i>	282	219	205	217	282	282
<i>Countries</i>	15	14	14	14	15	15
<i>Periods (Years)</i>	21	21	21	21	21	21

Note: *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Figure 3. Trade union density in the EU, 1999–2020.

Note: Union density is defined as the share of unionised workers in the total workforce. The series is derived from the databases of Visser (2019) and ILOSTAT.

Further Information:

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